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ECONOMICS OF MANAGEMENT EDUCATION IN INDIA: RETURNS TO INVESTMENT ANALYSIS APPROACH

Dr Fayaz Ahmad Bhat

Lecturer Economics,

Government of J & K Education Department , India

ABSTRACT

The theme of paper is nothing more than an attempt to evaluate the allocative efficiency of resources devoted to management education. Its utility lies mainly in indicating the investment characteristic of management education revealing the areas of high and low returns. The study will find out positive total and differential costs and benefits associated with various levels of management education with basic introduction of cost benefit (C-B) analysis. A historical update of C-B analysis and rate of return (RoR) studies has been briefly analyzed with reference to above theme. It also traces the need and importance of said theme. The paper will analyze the direct costs and benefits of management degree course in national capital territory region of Delhi. The differentials were also traced out by the cost and benefits structure of management degree at different levels, and schooling types including institution category. The returns to investment in management degree were calculated through standardized Mincerian earning function approach. The unit cost derived from the estimates of management degree course is INR 86650. The mean annual salary of employee with management degree is INR 5.54 lacs. The annual salary with some years of labour market experiences is much higher than the initial salary expected by the management graduates. The private RoR for management schooling year in IT industry is 12.2%. The interaction coefficient between years of management degree and labour market experience come out to be negative, indicating substitutability between the two.

Key words: Costs and Benefit Analysis, Management Education, Earning differential, Mincerian Earning Function.

Introduction

Education is the process of learning new skills, finding out new information or of understanding various phenomenon can be analysed by theories of cognition, theories of behaviour and through most social sciences disciplines, more specifically through economics. Economists compare the actuality of education system to the potential opportunities with resource available recognising that all resources have opportunity costs and benefits.

- The first role for the economists of education relates to the labour market. Education is a primary determinant of wages, included in the most estimates of earnings and for many it drives the demand of learning's and trainings. The apprenticeship, labour market and higher education are inter-linked at the micro economic level. Aggregating up the individual labour effects, education also have macroeconomic effects and raise economic growth.
- Second economists have a role in formulating behavioural and demand theory, studying how education changes behaviour and alters information sets by decision making process.
- The third role is in the study of educational organisations such as schools, colleges or universities with their technologies, using factor input, costs and revenue functions. The supply of education provision

will depend on all these aspects and the theory of the enterprise can be applied to describing such provision.

- The fourth role for economists is as market analysts. The equilibrium of the supply of and demand for education will depend on how the market is constituted: schools may be competitive or cartelised and education may be traded either through vouchers, loans or allocated by fiat. The efficiency and equity of these markets structures and exchanges mechanisms needs attention.
- Finally, economists have an important role as accountants. Education has become an increasingly important activity within all economies.

The economic methods available to economics of education are

A) Efficiency studies

- (i) Allocative internal efficiency
- (ii) Input choice efficiency
- (iii) Costs and benefits effectiveness analysis
- (iv) Modelling of the education production function
- (v) Demand and supply analysis

B) Costs and benefits benefit analysis

Among the above available methods, the costs and benefits of education are of crucial importance to education planners and policy makers. The inputs of education can be measured in terms of money and real resources that are used in the educational process namely time of teachers, students, other staff and books, materials, equipments and buildings. Since resources devoted have alternative opportunities, for using these resources which involve opportunity costs because choice necessarily involve giving up other opportunities. The costs of education to individual's students or their families include expenditure on fees, books, equipment and also earnings forgone. The costs of society is much wider and includes not only the wages and salaries of teachers and other staff, expenditure on books, equipment, raw material and building, but the forgone earnings of students which represent the output forgone by society as a whole. The costs of individual is called private costs while as costs of whole society is called social costs.

Another important distinction between current and capital expenditure, as they are both included in costs of education. Recurrent or current expenditure or costs include all expenditure on consumable goods and services which bring short term benefits and have to be regularly renewed. Capital costs or expenditure, on the other hand include the purchase of other durable assets such as building and equipment which are expected to yield benefits over a longer period. The purchase of capital goods may be considered as investment. Both current and capital expenditure can be measured in terms of actual or current, or in terms of constant price level. An analysis of trends in educational expenditure for example may be concerned either with trends in actual expenditure, or the expenditure expressed in terms of constant purchasing power.

Historical Background

The development of a society in general and an individual in particular is closely linked to the educational attainments of its people. The doctrine that has perhaps remained unquestioned over a period of time is that why development means different things to different people, but the importance of education as a facilitator for development is commonly agreed upon. The methodology of C-B analysis has been in existence since the turn of the century and was e.g., incorporated in the USA's River and Harbor Act of 1902. Blaug (1968) work is regarded as birth of economics of education, but in December 1960 when Schutlz delivered his presidential address 'Investment in Man' to the American Economic Association, laid foundations to it. There had been a stirring of interest in education by economists throughout the second half of the 1950s. Vaizey's pioneering work '*The Costs and Benefits of Education*' was published in 1958. In the same year as Friedrich Edding published his work in Germany entitled '*International Trends in Educational Expenditure*', which continental European writers usually treat as heralding the birth of the subject? In 1958 also, the present author as an undergraduate presented a paper on the economics of education entitled 'Investment in Human Capital', to the Cambridge University Political Economy Club: which made no great claims to originality, but quoted works, made some use of the concept of education as an investment. The paper also quoted passages in Marshall and

Smith which show that both the founding fathers of Anglo-Saxon economics were well aware of the similarity between investing in human resources through education or training and investing in physical capital.

In Indian context, Punchmukhi (1966) estimated the total costs of education in India 1950-51 to 1959-61. He assumed resource as well as opportunity costs of education. He estimated that total costs constituted 6.2% of GNP in 1959-60. Kothari made a study of total costs of education in India for three independent years 1950-51, 1955-56 and 1959-60. Kamat gave a good account of unit recurring costs at degree and PG level in University of Poona for the year 1964-65. Mathur's study aimed at analyzing the growth and variation in educational expenditure during 1951-61 with respect to objects, institutions, states, sources of management. He showed pattern of educational expenditure from different sources of educational finance and their relative performance of different states in education. The study revealed that the total expenditure increased by 20% and expenditure pupil increased by 162% during the period.

Pandith computed the social and private costs of resources used up in educational process in first three five year plan periods. For the first time in India, he made an attempt to estimate the capital costs of education by calculating the stock of physical capital. Further he highlighted the significance of neglected inputs, especially by time spent by student in education. The study revealed that the share of direct costs to total private costs has declined while the share of opportunity costs has risen over the period. Nanjundappa (1976) conducted the study on the university finances of Karnataka University, in relation to costs and performance of university. He found that there was a continuously rising gap between the costs and benefits of higher education and fees charged despite rise in unemployment in the graduates, PG's and severe maladjustment between output of the university and the needs of economy. Chalam (1978) analyzed the costs of education in colleges under the Andhra University. The major objective of the study was to examine and compare the different unit costs of education between colleges. He found the effect of students Socio-economic background on expenditure of education.

Ramanujan et-al study found that the salary accounted for more than 80% of total expenditure. Sharma provides the comparative analysis of the unit costs of large number of universities of general and professional education for a period 1974-75 to 1976-77. Geogre (1982) attempted to analyze the impact of household's economic background on the choice of courses by students and to estimate the private and social costs of obtaining higher education. He came out analysis with special reference Tamil Nadu for period 1960-76. Garg estimated unit costs of education for the Punjab University reference period was 1950-75. Pillai and Nair (1962) carried out a study on the history and problem of educational finance in Kerala, India University of Kerala. Nair studied the interrelationship among schools, education, demographic variables, employment and emigration with special reference to Kerala. Ramachandran attempted to analyze the problem of higher education in India with special reference to Kerala. The period of analysis was 1957-75. Mathew has examined in detail the sources and uses of funds of private colleges in Kerala for period 1972-86.

Combs and Hallack (1972) attempted to explain why C-B analysis has become imperative in the changing times, how educational costs behave like this how various educational system used costs analysis and with what results. Carnegie Commission on higher education (1973) prepared a report entitled as 'who pays, who benefits, who should pay'. Pickford (1975) discussed comprehensively the economic aspects of administration in university in U K. The main objective of his study was to investigate potential economies in the costs of producing students in a university. The first part of the study contained a detailed analysis of costs by activities such as training and research and courses of education. The part second of study explains the scope of the economies of scale to certain university courses.

The above cited studies are not specific to particular type of schooling years; there are huge differentials in costs and benefits of particular education category like technical professional degree and general education, mode of attaining degree i.e., public private etc. The objective of present study is to evaluate the allocative efficiency of resources devoted to education particularly management education. The study will find out positive total and differential costs and benefits associated with various levels of management education with basic introduction of cost benefit (C-B) analysis. A historical update of C-B analysis and rate of return (RoR) studies has been briefly analyzed with reference to above theme. The study also traces the need and importance of said theme. The paper will analyze the direct costs and benefits of management degree course in national capital territory region of

Delhi. The differentials were also traced out by the cost and benefits structure of management degree at different levels, and schooling types including institution category. The returns to investment in management degree were calculated through standardized Mincerian earning function approach.

Return to Investment Analysis to Higher Education: Mincerian Earning Function

The Mincerian Wage Equation (MEFn¹) is a popular model for analyzing how an individual's education and experience affect his or her wage. These method involves the fitting of a function of log wages (lnw)², using years of schooling, years of labour experience and its square as indifference variable (often weeks-worked or hours-worked are added as independent variables to this function as compensatory factors). The reason is that investment in human capital like other investments are only undertaken as long as long as RoR (not the absolute return) on the investment exceeds the discount rate. Log linearity of earnings as function of years of schooling is in fact a key empirical implication of human capital model (HCM) (Mincer 1958). The existing evidence generally supports the log earnings specification. Heckman and Polachek (1974) estimated Box-Cox Model and couldn't reject the log specification.

Tan and Paqueo (1989) using the MEFn, found returns to education in Philippines which were described as lower than the average for developing countries. The MEFn approach gave a private return (average overall education) of only 8.1%. Grootaert (1990) applied Mincer type functions to data for the Ivory Coast and found that secondary vocational and technical education (VTE) yielded a high private returns of 15.84% and social returns of only 3.86%. The post-secondary level for private returns was 21.2% against social returns of 4.46%. All the social returns were below the social opportunity cost of capital. Riveros (1990) calculated IRoR to education in Chile both via the standard approach and via a MEFn. The PRoR for primary, secondary and higher education were 27.6%, 11% and 10.3% respectively. McGavin (1991) presented updated RoR to education in Papua New Guinea. The PRoR to primary education was 37% and for university education it was 23%. All findings were significantly higher than those quoted earlier. Tannen (1991) used a MEFn Approach on data for working males only and found average PRoR averaging around 12 to 13% in Brazil. These were substantially lower than estimates mentioned above. Correction for probability of unemployment might reduce the finding by one or two percentage points. Regional data enabled the calculation of geographical variation but these were not substantial. Psacharopoulos and Alam (1991) found the average returns to education of 10.7% in Venezuela from MEFn. Returns were higher for workers in urban areas and had not fallen significantly over time, despite the educational expansion in Venezuela. Calculations via an Elaborate Method found somewhat higher figures up to 16.2% PRoR in the case of primary education, with some evidence of rates falling over previous decades. Jain (1991) also found weak support for the declining RoR hypothesis, especially when temporary, cyclical variations in local economies were taken in to account. Over the time it would also be necessary to drop a number of assumptions such as constant technology.

The above quoted studies has not taken particular branch of Higher education into consideration for C-B analysis and MEFn except few like Zhu (2010) estimated RoR to STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Medicine which also includes mathematics), LEM (Law, Economics and Management), COMB (those with degrees that combine more than one subject) and OSSAH (other social sciences, arts and humanities which includes languages). In Indian context no study of such kind is available.

Need and Importance of Study

The macro sphere of management degree education is taken into account. As it has reached to a stage where experimentation with variety of alternatives in cost and benefit structures, financing (both community and

¹ A basic assumption of the model is that all years of education generate an equal RoR to the student. This assumption implies a linear relationship between the log of earnings and the number of years of education. Second, we assume that the cost of an additional year of education equals the lost wages one might earn in that time. Finally, no accounting exists in this model for the quality of education received.

² Logs are typically used in econometric models for reasons of convenience or fit; there is strong theoretical rationale for using log earnings in HC earnings function regression. As pointed out by the Mincer (1958) education should have the multiplicative effect of HC in a simple model where identical individual maximize the present value of the future income, which is equalized by all educational levels in equilibrium

private), privatization and internationalization can be attempted. The allocation of resources to management education is a decision making process, which can benefit from the study of C-B structure to educational investment. Therefore C-B analysis to management education can be a crucial importance in developing a rational public/private policy towards investment in professional and technical education and more specifically in management education. In India the collection of literature highlighted above made us better understandable of the terminology of economies of education both at national and international level. We have understood some of the main controversies in empirical research in education economics especially in C-B analysis and are able to summarize the research evidence. We can explain and apply key economic concepts, methods and ideas to C-B analysis to management education. While providing examples of research evidences, later can evaluate the impact of educational policies and investment outcome of management education.

The huge demand for management degree holders on high salaries resulting mushroom growth of management colleges/universities/study centres, so urgent need is to trace out the trend of costs and benefits. The NCT being taken as sample space where all types of central, state, deemed, private and also centres with foreign university affiliations are found. The said area is centrally located where the huge demand of management education matches its supply. But still there exists gap i.e., India added nearly 20,000 colleges in a decade³ which translate into a growth of more than 150%. Number of degree granting universities doubled from 256 to 564, primarily due to deemed and private universities. India has a complex affiliation system where universities can have hundreds of public and private teaching colleges affiliated to it. Although number of students enrolled in higher education doubled from nearly 8.4 million to 17 million in a decade, it grew a slower pace than number of colleges which grew 2.5 times in the same period, creating a paradoxical situation of excess capacity in a country where gross enrolment ratio is less than 20%. Number of UGC/AICTE approved seats for student intake in management institutions in India grew by nearly 180% respectively in five years as compared to the growth of economy (Gross Domestic Product-GDP) by only about 50%⁴. Clearly, engineering and management institutions have grown at a pace much faster than the economy to absorb the talent. This in turn has created a situation of overcapacity, poor quality and unemployability of graduates. Given that many engineering cum management graduates go to high-growth, high-paying IT industry, this sign of overcapacity is troublesome and indicates that industry is headed for a major shake-up and consolidation.

In the current economic climate, there will be increasing pressure on policy makers for costs reduction and increased efficiency and there is likely to be more resistance to providing extra resources for educational projects. Educational staff will therefore even need more than before to make the best use of available resources, they need to examine carefully the full resource implications of any proposed new scheme, and to support their arguments with the quantitative as well as qualitative data wherever possible. C-B analysis can be powerful aid to achieving these aims.

Since the vast majority of educational spending is government financed or from the organised corporate sector, which keeps up-to-date estimates of the institutional expenditure or costs of education over a period of time. But the estimates regarding the private costs hardly exist in the educational C-B literature. As the students fee include all costs of tuition fee in schools, colleges and universities. There lies a great variation in the out of pocket costs structure. One of the points at issue is the role of public and private institutions. Both types of institutions exist side by side, but the question of ownership does not necessarily determine the way in which institution is financed. There is a debate whether publically owned colleges or universities should charge fees or not. Another area of disagreement is concerned with the question of fee differentials. Differentials fee and earnings can be charged which reflect costs and benefit differences. What are the factors responsible for

³ Increased from 12,806 in 2000-01 to 33,023 in 2010-11. UGC report "[Higher education in India at a glance](#)"

⁴

Program	Level of Course	2011-12	2007-08	Five Year plan Changes	Five Year Plan Changes (%)
Management	PG	249,710	89369	160341	179%
GDP (trillion US \$)		1.84	1.24	0.6	48%

Source: AICTE, World bank, CIA prepared by www.Dreducation.com

individual level variation in and out of pocket expenditure in education? What will determine the future course of expenditure and earnings trend? What will be the impact of this trend in out of pocket expenditure and earning differentials on quality and quantity of higher education level and more specifically on management education? These questions need in depth assessment at micro as well as at macro level in different educational settings.

Being a comparatively new field, where not much systematic work has been done so far in our country, especially in NCT, these kinds of studies will throw up interesting results. The present paper relates to both undergraduate and postgraduate courses in management education in various colleges and universities.

The key fundamental questions are

- What is the maximum management degree education costs (or more properly *expenditure*) burden currently being borne by the student and their families in various regions of country especially NCT, and what is the recent increase in these costs borne by students and families as opposed to governments or taxpayers? This question must consider any offsetting effects of means tested or otherwise targeted grants and student loans. What policy tools – e.g. need-based grants, loans, loan subsidies, very low or no tuition, subsidised lodging and food – are being employed to increase accessibility and what is known of their efficacy?
- The increasing tendency of earnings differentials from past two decades has taken the attention of economists to larger extend but economists and analysts in India has not succeed while estimating RoR or earnings of human capital endowments and more specifically to ICT sector. The paper is an attempt in this regard.
- How to analyze differentials by taking macro level experience of Indian ICT industry and look forward for causes there in.

So above all research gaps need to be evaluated through a unique systematic approach. The standard methodology of C-B analysis and MEFn is applied throughout, so that common inferences can be withdrawn and will be applicable for the policy making. An analysis of differences in costs and benefits of management degree with a varied setting i.e., the case study of NCT is highly important.

Sample Design, data Collection and Methodology

The proportionate random sampling technique was used to select the colleges/universities in NCT. The institutions are Government (both centrally and state sponsored), self financing and private assuming all other things constant. After selection of college, latter students were selected proportionately from management degree, including Bachelor of Business Administration, Master of Business Administration, Bachelor of International Business and Finance, Masters of International Finance and Master of International Business, accounts (Chartered Accounts /Company Secretary ship /Cost and Works Accounts), computers (Bachelor of Computer Applications/Master of Computer applications), engineering and technology (Electronics, Communication and Information Technology graduates) and general category students. But the paper is further extended for analysis purpose to management degree holders only. The proportionate percentage of students has been taken from open and distance learning (ODL) mode. The ODL and online courses are gaining momentum in India especially in management degree education. The study focuses on the management degree both at bachelors and masters level with relative comparison with others. As mentioned above the study takes into account the out of pocket expenditure of students into consideration, the description of cost structure, here the information were obtained wide range. The information on socio-economic background of students, cost of degree education, salary expectations and household asset information were collected. The sample size was 480 students including 160 from management degree holders only. The percentage share of students taken from different colleges is in proportion to their relative percentage share in IT industry. The unit cost variable of higher education is an effective measure of cost of education. The increase in the direct cost of the schooling reduces the probability of a student to attend school. The financial constraints too adversely affect the schooling outcomes. Therefore it is designed to provide baseline information for policy planning on education in order to enhance internal efficiency in management education system.

Table no. 1: **Unit Cost of Higher Technical/professional Education in NCT Delhi**

S. no	Schooling Type	Unit Cost	Bachelors	Masters
1	Accounts	70413	50326	71199*
2	Computers	96632	65992	127273
3	Management	86650	83721	91041
4	Technology	88041	80326	103471
5	Total	81025	70878	98246

Source: Primary Survey (2011-12)

The measurement of employees earning differentials through rate of return to management education is the key focus of study. The data required for the analysis were collected from respondents of the case area. Identification of the sampling units (companies) and there from the respondents (employees) were the primary requirement. However education category-wise stratification was taken care of to facilitate the earning differential comparisons. A representative sample was drawn from NCT region of Delhi. The reason being, highest percentage of employees with management degree, huge attrition rate, increasing capital deepening technologies, competitiveness nature and the basic preposition of marginal productivity labour is equal to wages do exist in industry.

The employee earnings differentials with respect to human capital endowments, being the focus for the present paper, employee strength were taken as standard for selection of the companies⁵. The four hundred and fifty employees were selected from the listed employees, who have management degree background. A primary survey was conducted through personal investigation method/enumerators questionnaire method, or electronic questionnaire/web link to get information on variables required for the study. The data were collected from all locations of NCT (Noida, Gurgaon, Delhi, Ghaziabad, Faridabad, and Greater Noida)⁶.

Statistics reveal that 79.7% employees/respondents were men; whereas 20.3% were females. The sample is not equally distributed. The reason is quite obvious because IT industry is traditionally man dominated and due its nature and composition. The estimated mean age worked out as 29.92 years, 31 years and 27 years for the total sample respondents, male respondents and female respondents respectively. The reason for low mean age is that IT sector employees are of younger generation possesses the technical skills.

The below estimates clearly indicates that the females earn more salary than men but in case of management degree holder employees is the difference is large, the reasons identified were requirements of travelling, were females are not used to.

⁵ The list of IT companies was taken from NASSCOM directory and then classified according to employee strength. The companies were divided into two categories. The first set includes all companies whose employee strength on March 2010 was below 100000 and second category includes those companies with employee strength above 100000. The five companies were selected from each group. The ten companies which have strong footing in terms of financial and employee's strength in India especially in NCT were selected. Selected Company's profiles were sketched through personal interview to HR's/managers of companies. It was found that these companies were almost similar in operation and in their services. A list of employees working in NCT offices along with their basic information like name, contact, and designation was collected from managers/HR. The objective of study was to cover earning differentials and estimating RoR, so educational type (stream) was taken as base for selection of employees.

⁶ According to the Software parks of India (STPI), the regions generate software revenue of rupee 5900 crore (ranks second after Bangalore). This is followed by enormous increase in the earnings of employee's, so it is worth studying the factors behind the vast differentials in earnings of employees. The productivity levels have increased enormously within industry; this is followed by increased differentials in earnings.

Table no. 2 Salary Differentials With Respect to Education Category

S.no	Schooling Type	Yearly Mean Wages Rate (INR Lacs)	Yearly Mean Wages Rate		Hourly Mean Wage Rate ⁷ (INR)	Hourly Mean Wage Rate	
			Male	Female		Male/	Female (INR)
1	Accounts	6.15	5.0	7.9	248	201	318
2	Computers	6.30	6.6	5.4	254	266	217
3	Management	7.30	8.2	5.7	294	330	229
4	Technology	10.3	9.9	14.8	415	399	596
5	Other General	3.80	3.0	7.3	153	120	294
6	Total Aggregate	6.77	6.54	8.22	272	263	330
7	Total Professional /Technical	7.515	7.425	8.45	302.75	299	340

Source: Primary Survey (2011-12)

Table No. 3: Mean Salary with Respect to Institute Type (INR lacs Annual)

S. No	Institute Type	Mean	Male	Female
1	Central	5.8	5.9	5.4
2	State	4.25	4.9	3.7
3	Deemed	3.65	3.65	3.65
4	Private	5.95	5.2	6.9

Source: Primary Survey (2011-12)

On the average men from centrally sponsored universities fetch highest salary than other. The mean salary of private (institute type) was highest because females with their highest attained degrees from private institutes receive highest mean salary of INR 6.9 lacs. The female's socio-economic background in this category is very rich.

Table no. 4: Comparison between Actual and Expected Salary by Schooling Type

S. No	Schooling Type	Yearly Salary (Actual)	Yearly Salary (Expected)	Hourly Salary (Actual)	Hourly Salary (Expected)
1	Accounts	615000	600192	248	242
2	Computers	630000	412932	254	166
3	Management	730000	384996	294	155
4	Technology	103000	592668	415	238
5	Total	751500	497697	302.75	200

Source: Primary Survey (2011-12)

The above estimates clearly shows us that students mean expected starting salary is much lesser than what they are expected to get after getting a job with certain amount of on the job experiences, taking the case of management education it is 52.73% higher than the expected average mean salary.

Empirical Estimates of Model MEFn: Schooling Type Management

The estimates from the MEFn with all variables for the Management category (schooling type) employees are shown below along with the descriptive statistics⁸:

⁷ T_{ij} = Employees Yearly Income / Working Hours Per Year

According to ILO norm there are forty eight (48) working hours in a week i.e., six days a week, which suits the IT industry of NCT region, therefore taken for derivation of hourly wage rate. The total working days taken for said calculation is 310, keeping 55 days as holidays. This amounts to be 2480 working hours.

⁸ Descriptive Statistics and Model Summary

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N

Table No.5: Empirical Estimates: *MEFn* (Schooling Type Management)

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	-.123	.816		-.151	.880
Si	.122	.047	.168	2.588	.010
X _i	.115	.081	1.352	1.423	.155
X ²	.001	.001	.147	1.026	.306
S _i .X _i	-.010	.005	-1.931	-2.127	.034
Sex	-.064	.054	-.055	-1.186	.236
At _r	.032	.017	.101	1.830	.068
Ad _n	.036	.020	.082	1.796	.073
T _n	-.009	.015	-.029	-.640	.522

Dependent Variable: lnw_i

Source: Primary Survey (2011-12)

The results revealed that the PRoR to management background employees is 12.2 % with high significance level. The post school investment behaviour including experiences (X), additional degrees (Ad_n) and trainings (T_n) have strong positive correlation with earnings. All other variable coefficients are positively related with dependent variable except T_n, sex and interaction term. It shows that in case of management background employees the years of schooling can be substituted by years of experience in terms of their impact on earnings. The experience square (X_i²) coefficient with positive sign indicates positive slope, which reveals that with the increase in years of experience the earnings also increase. So with unit increase in experiences there is increase in salary of employees.

The above results can be compared with two studies Samuels (1972) and Zhu (2010) in terms of complete similarity in specifications.

Samuel (1972) applied C-B Analysis to Management education, evaluating the two year post-graduate programme of IIM Ahmadabad India. He found that even at a rate of discount of 13% the programme of institute yields a positive social net present value through a combination of import substitution and income creation approach. His estimates are in line with the present estimates. But his estimates of net present value are based on alternate assumptions regarding rate of discount, alpha coefficient, foreign exchange, elasticity of demand for management education in India etc.

Zhu (2010) estimated RoR to STEM, LEM, COMB and OSSAH. He found it as 10.7%, 13.8%, 12.9% and 10.8% respectively, which are comparable with the results estimated in present study. In the present study estimates of the RoR's management degree holder employees is 12.2% is similar to his estimates.

Limitations of study

The study has focused only direct costs and benefits of management schooling years. The direct institutional cost has not taken into consideration, which would have been more important in case of estimating social costs of education or social RoR. The indirect costs in-terms of foregone earnings have been taken by

LnWi	1.590819	.48876278	450
Si	17.08	.676	450
X _i	8.238	5.7356	450
X ²	1.0070E2	139.94629	450
S _i .X _i	1.4077E2	97.61101	450
Sex	1.22	.418	450
At _r	1.89	1.568	450
Ad _n	.53	1.107	450
T _n	.62	1.470	450

Mincerian Model. The study has delimited to small sample size, which will be small size for any policy generalization.

Conclusion

The C-B analysis in education especially in management education can serve a variety of purposes in educational planning including, testing the economic feasibility of expansion plans, proposals or targets, projecting future levels of educational costs and benefits. It can estimate the costs and benefits of alternative policies and the educational reforms or innovations. The wide differentials in wages shown above are said to provide a rationale for extensive periods of jobs search particularly in Indian Information Technology industry. These wage differentials can possibly allow market to provide incentive for individuals to develop and maintain appropriate levels of skills. The RoR estimates alone cannot be used for educational planning. It must be supplemented by manpower demand forecasting. This is because RoR indicates only the direction of change of the educational output. It says nothing on the required amount of change of the educational output. A set of RoR could be used for educational planning only. Most public decisions related to investment in schooling entail changes that can't be considered as marginal. The transition to work from school will be improved through inducement to study. The career counselling cells especially at universities/institutes campus can reduce hiring costs to companies. The Indian companies spend INR 25500 per hire of employee. The internships programmes of companies can be fruitful for prospective employees to build skills which particular industry requires. These types of programmes will reduce the hiring cost.

In future studies are needed, which can assess the inter-country/regional disparities in human capital attainments. Studies are also needed to understand the potentials skills to be gained from educational and training qualification and their interpretation by employees. The existing mismatch between higher educated graduates and labour market requirements call for in-depth research work on the possibility of substitutability between levels of higher education and on-the-job labour market experiences. We feel that the institutions of high learning, research and development like UNESCO, NUEPA, UGC, AICTE etc should assist some universities/institutes/industry and individuals to conduct such kind of investigations periodically on the basis of standardized techniques.

References

1. Achara, Sarthi (1996), "Access and Returns to Education: An Analysis of Maharashtra", Journal of Educational Planning and Administration, Vol. 10 No. 4, pp. 383-396.
2. Blaug, M. (1969), "Economics of Education-2", Selecting Readings. Penguin Books Publications.
3. Al-Qadri, S. S. (1989), "Returns to Education, Sectoral Pay Differentials and Determinants in Kuwait", Journal of Developmental Economics Vol. 8 No. 3, pp. 263-276
4. Blaug, M. (1968), "Economics of Education-1", Penguin Books Publications.
5. Blaug, M. (1970), "An Introduction to Economics of Education", Allen land. The Penguin Press.
6. Card, David and John E. Dinardo (2002), "Skill Based Technological Change and Rising Wage Inequality: Some Problems and Puzzles" Working Paper No. 8769 New York National Bureau of Economic Research <http://www.nber.org>.
7. Carrol, A. B. & Ihnen, A. I. (1967), "Costs & Returns for two years of Post Secondary Technical Schooling: A Pilot study", Journal of Political Economy, Vol. 75 No. 6, pp. 862-873.
8. Chalam, K S (1978), "Expenditure on University Education", Journal of Higher Education, Vol. 4 No. 2, pp. 201-224.
9. Chiswick, B. R. (2003), "Jacob Mincer, Experience and the Distribution of Earning," Review of Economics of the Household Vol. 1 No. 4, pp. 343-361.
10. Chung, Tsung Ping (2004), "The Returns to Education and Trainings: Evidence from the Malaysian Life Survey", Pacific Economic Review, Vol. 9 No. 2, pp. 103-116.
11. Combs and Jacques Hallack (1972), "Managing Educational Costs and Benefits" Oxford University Press London.
12. Davis, B. and Verry, D. (1976), "University Costs and Output", Elseview-Amsterdam Publication.
13. Duraisamy, P. (2006), "Unit Costs of Vocational and Academic Education at Higher Secondary Level in Tamil Nadu", Manpower Journal, IAMR publication. Vol. XLI No.4. Special Issue on Vocational and Professional Education.

14. Duraisamy, P. and M. Duraisamy (1995), "Returns to Higher Education in India", *Journal of Educational Planning and Administration*, Vol. 9 No. 1, pp. 57-68.
15. Duraisamy, P. and M. Duraisamy (1996), "Substitutability between Education and Experience in Labour Market Experience", *Journal of Educational Planning and Administration*, Vol, 10 No. 3, pp. 271-279.
16. Eckkaus, R. S. et al. (1974), "An Appraisal of Calculation of Rates of Return to Higher Education", New York: Mcgraw Hill Publications.
17. Grootaert, C. (1990), "Returns to Formal and Informal Vocational Education in Cote D'Ivoire, The Role of Structure of labour Market", *Economics of Education Review* Vol. 9 No. 4, pp. 309-319.
18. Kothari, V. N. (1966), "Factor Costs and Benefits of Education in India", *Indian Economic Journal* Vol. 13 No. 5 pp. 631-47.
19. Heckman, J., J. Lance, J. Lochner and Petra E. Todd (2003), "Fifty Years of Mincerian Earning Regressions", Working Paper No. 9732 New York National Bureau of Economic Research.
20. Heckman, J. and Lance J. Lochner, and Petra E. Todd (2006), "Earnings Functions, Rates of Return and Treatment Effects: The Mincer Equation and Beyond" *Handbook of the Economics of Education*, Elsevier.
21. Mathur, M. V. (1974) "A Study in Costs and Benefits of Education in India during 1951-61", in M B Bush [ed.], "A Survey of Research in Education", Centre for Advanced Studies in Education M S University Baroda India.
22. Merrett, S. (1971), "The Rate of Return to Education: A Critique", In book *Education and Economics of Human Capital* by Ronold Wykstra. The Free Press New York pp.196-213.
23. Mincer, J. (1958), "Investment in Human Capital and Personal Income Distribution", *Journal of Political Economy* Vol. 66, pp. 281-302.
24. Mincer, J. (1962), "On the Job Training: Costs, Returns and Some Implications", *Journal of Political Economy Supplement*, Vol. 70 No. 5, pp. 50-79.
25. Mincer, J. (1970), "Distribution of Labour Incomes: A Survey with Special Reference to the Human Capital Approach", *Journal of Economic Literature* Vol. 8 No. 1, pp. 1-26.
26. Mincer, J. (1974a), "Schooling Experience and Earnings", Columbia University Press, New York.
27. Mincer, J. (1962), "On the Job Training: Costs, Returns and Some Implications", *Journal of Political Economy Supplement* Vol. 70 No. 5, pp. 50-79.
28. Mishra, S. K. and Panda, N. M. (2004), "Unit Costs of Higher Education: A Case Study of Northern Hill University", *Journal of Educational Planning and Administration* Vol. XIV No. 1, pp. 269-284.
29. Nanjundappa (1976), "Working of University Finances", Sterling Publication New Delhi.
30. Pandith, H. N. (1972), "Costs and Benefits Analysis of Education in India-Private and Social Participation", *Indian Education Review* Vol. 7 No. 2.
31. Patrinos, H. A., Cris Rido-cano and Chris Sakellariou (2006), "Estimating the Returns to Education: Accounting for Heterogeneity in Ability" World Bank Policy Research Working Paper 4040.
32. Paul, Samuel (1972), "An Application of Cost-Benefit Analysis to Management Education", *Journal of Political Economy* Vol. 80 No. 2, pp. 328-346.
33. Psacharopoulos, G. (1973), "Returns to Education: An International Comparison", Amsterdam Elsevier Scientific Publication Company.
34. Psacharopoulos, G. (1985), "Returns to Education: A Further International Update and Implication", *The Journal of Human Resources*, Vol. 20 No. 4, pp. 583-597.
35. Punchmukhi, P. R. (1966), "Educational Capital in India", *Indian Economic Journal* Vol. 12 No. 3, pp. 306-14.
36. Rao, M. J. and R. C. Datta (1989), "Rates of Return in the Indian Private Sector", *Economics Letters* Vol. 30, pp. 373-378.
37. Schultz, T. W. (1968), "The Rate of Return in Allocating Investment Resources to Education", *Economic Papers: A Journal of Applied Economics and Policy* Vol. E1 No. 27, pp. 40-55.
38. Tsang, M. C. (1995), "Costs and Benefits Analysis in Education", in Cornoy M. (ed). "International Handbook of Economics of Education", Second Edition. Pergamon UK.
39. Tilak, J. B. J. (1979), "Schooling, Experience and Earnings", *Margin* Vol. 11 No. 4, pp. 82-
40. Tilak, J. B. G. (2006), "Analysis of Costs of Education in India", *International Journal of Education Development* Vol. 8 No. 1, pp. 25-42.
41. Tilak, J. B. G. (1995), "Costs and Financing of Education in India – A Review of Issues, Problems and Prospects", UNDP Discussion paper series no. 5.
42. Unni, Jeemol (1996), "Returns to Education by Gender among Wage Employee in Urban India", *Journal of Educational Planning and Administration* Vol. X No. 2 pp. 153-172